

ON THE PREPARATION OF IODO-CHLORO-OXYQUINOLINE

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A new method is described for the preparation of 5-chloro-7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline.

5-Chloro-7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline, first introduced as odourless iodoform, has come to stay as an internal antiseptic for amoebic infection (Leake, *J. Amer. Med. Assoc.*, 98, 195; David *et al.*, *ibid.*, 100, 1858). A survey of the literature did not reveal any method for its preparation excepting one or two patented processes dealing mainly with one or other of the intermediate compounds used in the preparation, or describing a process that could be used in the preparation of such intermediates, (B. P., 3915; Ghosh and others, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 354). The present process starts with acetanilide which is chlorinated to *p*-chloroacetanilide (Orton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 1050) from which in turn is prepared 4-chloro-2-nitrophenol in two ways: (i) *p*-chloroacetanilide is nitrated to 4-chloro-2-nitroacetanilide which on hydrolysis with a concentrated solution of sodium hydroxide is directly oxidised to 4-chloro-2-nitrophenol. Evidently the presence of the NO₂ group in the *ortho* position to the amino group in 4-chloro-2-nitroacetanilide facilitates the oxidation; (ii) *p*-chloroacetanilide is hydrolysed to *p*-chloroaniline with sulphuric acid and the solution after diazotisation in the usual way is poured into dilute nitric acid. On decomposition of the diazo solution on the water-bath, good yields of 4-chloro-2-nitrophenol are obtained. Only one molecule of nitric acid is necessary for one molecule of *p*-chloroacetanilide and isolation of intermediate products is unnecessary. This reaction of decomposition of diazo compounds in presence of nitric acid is being studied for the preparation of other important nitrophenols.

For the preparation of 5-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline, the use of the corresponding amine for the Skraup's reaction could be dispensed with as in other well known industrial processes (Alizarin Blue from Alizarin Orange etc.). Ghosh and others (*loc. cit.*) have prepared 5-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline from 4-chloro-2-nitrophenol using only sulphuric acid and glycerine but it is found practically impossible to control the reaction particularly when tackling large quantities of the nitrophenol. The addition of acetic acid (Cohn and Gustavson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2709) to the reaction mixture not only makes the reaction smooth but also greatly improves the yield. The iodination of the chlorohydroxyquinoline is effected by the addition of dilute acid to a mixture of a solution of the base and iodine in alkali. The base is usually dissolved in potassium hydroxide and iodine in sodium hydroxide.

5-Chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline gives insoluble precipitates of definite composition with metals and its applicability as a reagent is being investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Chloro-2-nitroacetanilide.—Use of acetic acid and acetic anhydride as employed by Remmers (*Ber.*, 1874, 7, 437) for the nitration of *p*-chloroacetanilide was found unnecessary. Nitration was effected as usual with nitric acid in sulphuric acid solution in 85% yield, m.p. 104° (from alcohol).

4-Chloro-2-nitrophenol.—(i) Crude, moist nitration product from *p*-chloroacetanilide (225 g.) was refluxed in an iron flask with caustic soda (300 g.) in water (600 c.c.) as long as ammonia was evolved (40 hours). The reaction product was transferred into a flask and the red solid residue of the sodium salt of the nitrophenol was dissolved out from the flask with hot water. After cooling, the sodium salt was filtered and dissolved in boiling water, filtered if necessary, cooled somewhat and the nitrophenol precipitated with hydrochloric acid, yield 70% (calculated on *p*-chloroacetanilide), m.p. 86° (from alcohol).

(ii) *p*-Chloroacetanilide (340 g.) was refluxed with a solution of sulphuric acid (340 c.c., *d* 1.84) and water (1700 c.c.) for 5 hours. After cooling to below 5° a solution of sodium nitrite (140 g.) in water (600 c.c.) was added with stirring and cooling. The diazo solution was next poured into a solution of nitric acid (140 c.c., *d* 1.4) in water (1400 c.c.) in a flask provided with a condenser. After some time the solution was heated on a water-bath and as soon as decomposition commenced the flask was removed from the water-bath. Evolution of nitrogen gradually became vigorous and eventually subsided. Towards the end, the solution was again heated on the water-bath to complete the reaction. Solid residue in the flask and the condenser was collected the next day and distilled in steam. Pure 4-chloro-2-nitrophenol collected in the receiver, m.p. 86°, yield 60.62% on *p*-chloroacetanilide.

5-Chloro-8-Hydroxyquinoline.—4-Chloro-2-nitrophenol (450 g.), acetic acid, glycerine and sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84) (900 c.c. of each) were taken in a 6 litre flask provided with a condenser and heated in an oil-bath at 150-160° for 8 hours. After cooling, the mass was thoroughly extracted with water and dilute sulphuric acid. The aqueous extract was filtered and nearly neutralised with sodium hydroxide and finally the mineral acid was decomposed with sodium acetate. The solid was collected, dissolved again in sulphuric acid and subjected to distillation in steam to remove traces of 4-chloro-2-nitrophenol. The base was again precipitated as above, filtered and washed, m.p. 123° (alcohol), yield 60% theoretical.

5-Chloro-7-iodo-8-Hydroxyquinoline.—5-Chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline (300 g.) was dissolved in a solution of potassium hydroxide (110 g.) in water (6 litres). After heating to boiling the solution was filtered and a solution of iodine (350 g.) in sodium hydroxide (150 g.) in water (3 litres) was mixed with the solution of the base. Dilute acetic acid was slowly run in until acid, while the solution was kept thoroughly stirred. After stirring for another hour the mixture was left overnight and the separated solid filtered and washed next day. The solid was again stirred with water while a solution of sodium thiosulphate was gradually dropped in. When excess of iodine was discharged, the solid was filtered, washed with water and finally with alcohol, m.p. of crude product 175°. Crystallised from benzol it melts at 178-79°, yield 90.84%. (Found: Cl, 12.0; I, 41.0. Calc. for C_8H_6ONCl : Cl, 11.63; I, 41.63 per cent).

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